

1 Ten Simple Rules for Implementing

2 Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs)

3 Justine Vandendorpe (ORCID: 0000-0002-9421-8582)¹, Beatrix Adam (ORCID: 0000-0002-
4 8431-6613)¹, Jeanne Wilbrandt (ORCID: 0000-0002-0363-3837)², Birte Lindstädt (ORCID:
5 0000-0002-8251-1597)¹, Konrad U. Förstner (ORCID: 0000-0002-1481-2996)^{1,3}

6 ¹ ZB MED - Information Centre for Life Sciences, Gleueler Str. 60, 50931 Cologne, Germany

7 ² Leibniz Institute on Aging – Fritz Lipmann Institute, Beutenbergstr. 11, 07745 Jena,
8 Germany

9 ³ TH Köln – University of Applied Sciences, Claudiusstr. 1, 50678 Cologne, Germany

10

11 **Corresponding author**

12 Konrad Förstner

13 Gleueler Str. 60, 50931 Cologne

14 foerstner@zbmed.de

15

16 Introduction

17 An Electronic Lab Notebook (ELN) is a software tool for documenting laboratory
18 experiments, research data and processes. ELNs are set to replace paper lab notebooks as
19 part of the ongoing digital transformation [1].

20 ELNs offer many benefits over physical lab notebooks. First, ELNs are connected to a
21 networked digital environment [2] through their import and export functions and seamless
22 interfaces to other programs. ELNs can therefore play a central role in an institution's
23 Research Data Management (RDM) strategy. Second, ELNs enable researchers to

24 collaborate [3], whether within their own group or with others, through a common medium.
25 Third, ELNs make an important contribution to Good Research Practice (GRP) [4] by
26 facilitating the tracking, tracing and documentation of research processes and results
27 through time. ELNs also prevent data loss and guarantee data security. Finally, ELNs
28 support the FAIR data principles [5], for instance through the assignment of metadata, tags
29 and Persistent Identifiers (PIDs).

30 In order to successfully implement an ELN in your institution, we recommend that you
31 involve staff from different areas (i.e., researchers, professors, lab managers and assistants,
32 IT experts, librarians and staff council) at all stages of product selection and evaluation to
33 achieve the greatest possible consensus.

34 The following ten rules offer guidance on implementing an ELN in your institution, bearing in
35 mind that each institution may require a solution tailored to its specific needs. We also
36 discuss the benefits of open-source ELNs and the importance of standardisation.

37 Rule 1: Gather information

38 There are many resources available to help you familiarise yourself with the ELNs currently
39 available.

40 For example, ZB MED provides an ELN Guide [6] designed to support research
41 infrastructure teams and researchers in selecting an ELN. The ELN Guide also includes
42 helpful references. Together with the University and State Library Darmstadt, ZB MED also
43 created the ELN Finder [7], an interactive tool for filtering ELNs based on 40 criteria. The
44 Harvard Longwood Medical Area Research Data Management Working Group also provides
45 an ELN Comparison Matrix [8], while Labfolder offers a guide [9] highlighting five ELNs.

46 You can also use the working groups, networks, mailing lists, and best-practice examples
47 listed in Table 1 to help you select and use an ELN. Joining a working group is a good way
48 to exchange information and find out what solutions other users have developed, such as
49 discipline-specific adaptations.

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51 **Table 1.** Communities and resources focusing on ELNs.

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Name	Type	Range	URL
ELB.nrw	Working group	Germany	https://wiki.hhu.de/ display/ELB/ ELB.nrw+Startseite
National Research Data Infrastructure working group on ELNs	Working group	Germany	https://www.nfdi.de/ section-infra/? lang=en
Ouvrir la science - Cahiers de laboratoire électroniques	Working group	France	https:// www.ouvriirlascience .fr/cahiers-de- laboratoire- electroniques/
Research Data Alliance (RDA) - Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions IG	Network	International	https://www.rd- alliance.org/groups/ research-data- architectures- research-institutions- ig
RDA - Electronic Laboratory Notebooks	Network	International	https://www.rd- alliance.org/ electronic-

Challenges and steps to solutions			laboratory-notebooks-challenges-and-steps-solutions
The ELN Consortium	Consortium	International	https://github.com/TheELNConsortium
Elabnotebook	Mailing list	Germany	https://listserv.gwdg.de/mailman/listinfo/elabnotebook
German Research Network	Mailing list	Germany	eln@listserv.dfn.de
UK Education and Research communities	Mailing list	UK	https://www.jiscmail.ac.uk/cgi-bin/webadmin?A0=RESEARCHNOTTEBOOKS
NFDI4Chem, Chemotion	Best-practice example	Germany	[6]
University Medicine Göttingen, RSpace	Best-practice example	Germany	[6]
ETH Zurich, openBIS	Best-practice example	Switzerland	[6]
University of	Best-practice	UK	[6]

Edinburgh, RSpace	example		
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54 Rule 2: Define selection criteria

55 To select ELNs for testing, we suggest that you define selection criteria that reflect the needs
56 of your institution and lab(s). By comparing your list of criteria with the features offered by
57 available ELNs, you can systematically reduce the number of ELNs to test. You can also
58 filter the results of the ELN Finder [7] based on your criteria to see which tool(s) it suggests.

59 This section covers what we consider to be the most important criteria; a full list of criteria
60 can be found in the appendix (S1 Appendix).

61 First, choose between a proprietary and open-source ELN. Open-source ELNs offer the
62 benefits of digital sovereignty [4], though they can be time-consuming to run and maintain
63 and may require the purchase of server hardware unless managed by a service provider.
64 Open-source ELNs do not have a fixed, vendor-defined set of features, and you will be
65 dealing with a community of developers instead of a single vendor. Finally, open-source
66 ELNs may lack support services and could complicate the task of meeting regulatory
67 requirements.

68 Proprietary ELNs offer the benefits of being developed by vendors who regularly update their
69 ELN and provide training and support services. On the other hand, proprietary ELNs are
70 expensive, and the vendor may go out of business or raise their prices. Additionally,
71 proprietary ELNs use proprietary formats, which may increase the risk of vendor lock-in (i.e.
72 where users become dependent on the ELN and are unable to move their data to another
73 ELN without significant migration costs [10]). To mitigate this risk, you should make sure
74 your chosen ELN allows you to export and archive all your data and/or the entire ELN in
75 open formats [4] (e.g., .xml, .csv, .png, .svg). There is currently no universally accepted open

76 exchange format, but there are standardisation initiatives (e.g., Standards4ELN [11], The
77 ELN Consortium [12] with its ELN File Format [13]).

78 You will also need to choose between cloud-hosted Software as a Service (SaaS) and
79 locally hosted, on-premises solutions. SaaS gives you the ability to use the ELN without the
80 need for your own infrastructure [1], but it is expensive [4], and data control and security
81 remain in the hands of the ELN provider (check your funder/institutional policy to see if you
82 are allowed to use such solutions) [1]. On-premises solutions give you full control over data
83 and security protocols, but require dedicated IT staff (e.g., for administration).

84 Finally, you should consider the performance and stability of both the ELN and the
85 company/developer community [1] by answering the following questions:

- 86 ● How long has the company/developer community existed?
- 87 ● Does it have enough capital investment to withstand crises?
- 88 ● Can it provide references?
- 89 ● How many people does it employ? Does it have a professional development team?
- 90 ● Do its employees have a research background and/or extensive experience in the
91 lab?
- 92 ● Does it state in its terms and conditions that users will have access to their data if the
93 company/developer community goes under or is sold? [1]

94 Rule 3: Test for usability

95 Usability testing is a technique used to evaluate ELNs [14] by conducting extensive tests that
96 are as close to reality as possible. This testing phase should help you to determine the
97 suitability of ELNs in an everyday working environment [1] and to assess where your risk lies
98 in choosing a particular ELN.

99 We recommend testing the ELN in parallel with the use of a physical lab notebook to (1)
100 determine the extent to which real workflows can be implemented in the ELN, (2) determine
101 whether the ELN can actually produce the required documentation, (3) document the

102 usability testing phase to justify the selection process afterwards, and (4) prevent data loss if
103 the tested ELN is not selected.

104 For this usability testing phase, we suggest that you first set up a test team of researchers
105 and lab assistants. Ideally, this test team would meet weekly with the IT coordinators and
106 data stewards. Next, select the workflows and prepare a test questionnaire (see ours in S2
107 Appendix). It may also be helpful to create a matrix of criteria and ELNs to tick off what has
108 already been tested. Finally, you need to determine the order in which the ELNs will be
109 tested.

110 We recommend taking an initial look at a wide range of ELNs and then pre-selecting two or
111 three tools to test over a period of three to six months, depending on how long it takes to
112 gain sufficient knowledge of the tools' suitability. Almost all companies will provide a trial
113 version of their ELN on request.

114 Rule 4: Introduce the ELN

115 Before introducing a proprietary ELN, you must first acquire the necessary licence. The next
116 step – for both proprietary and open-source ELNs – is to ensure a signed agreement is in
117 place between management and staff to prevent the ELN from being used to monitor staff.
118 You should also involve your institution's data protection officer and staff council in this
119 process in order to ensure compliance with institutional regulations and the General Data
120 Protection Regulation (GDPR).

121 Introduction of the software itself starts with ensuring that all technical requirements are met
122 (e.g., a stable wireless internet connection, suitable end devices with up-to-date hardware
123 and software [4]). You then need to establish and execute a rollout plan, which could include
124 the following steps: setting up the software, administering the system, troubleshooting,
125 distributing the ELN to labs, providing support, and applying updates as and when required.
126 Users, disseminators and multipliers need to be trained, and support services need to be set

127 up (e.g., wiki, hotline, FAQ and key contacts). The final step in introducing the tool is to
128 establish an offboarding procedure to ensure that outgoing user data is properly archived [4].

129 Rule 5: Collect feedback

130 Feedback from researchers and lab assistants can be gathered in stages. First, monitor
131 usage of the ELN to determine whether it is well accepted by the labs. If a group is not using
132 the ELN much, identify the reason and try to support the group. Second, visit individual labs
133 to get detailed feedback. The focus here is on the interaction between the research staff and
134 data stewards responsible for the ELN. The aim is to identify where support is needed and
135 how processes (e.g., documentation, ergonomics) could be improved. Third, establish a
136 systematic feedback collection process based on a questionnaire, an interview or group
137 discussions. This will help you to decide which new developments and/or product
138 modifications should be commissioned. Even at times when you are not collecting feedback,
139 keep the communication channels open. Ongoing support is key to successful
140 implementation [4].

141 Rule 6: Provide efficient documentation

142 ELNs offer features and functions that can provide significant time savings and knowledge
143 transfer in day-to-day lab work. These typically include the ability to create templates,
144 automatically record instrument results [15], retrieve data from databases for active data,
145 capture unstructured data, annotate raw data without having to switch between different
146 media formats, and add tags. Make sure you know how to use the ELN as efficiently as
147 possible so that you can pass on any tips and tricks.

148 Rule 7: Integrate the ELN in your RDM strategy

149 As a comprehensive data documentation tool, the ELN can play a central role in your
150 institution's RDM strategy. ELNs allow templates to be created for data collection and
151 facilitate the enrichment of data with metadata. ELNs also allow data to be captured as early
152 as possible and fed directly into an analysis pipeline [4]. The assignment of Persistent
153 Identifiers (PIDs) can also be incorporated into ELN systems. ELNs facilitate backup,
154 publication and archiving [15] by providing the means to prepare data for these steps and by
155 linking to reference management software, databases [3], repositories [15] and digital
156 preservation systems. This can help you to meet the requirements of funders and publishers
157 to make your data reusable. Finally, ELNs can prove provenance [3] through audit trails and
158 documentation of both data generation and equipment used.

159 To facilitate the integration of the ELN into your RDM strategy, there are a number of
160 requirements to consider. First, you may need a location to run your ELN and a location to
161 store your data. You will need policies for backing up data and preserving it for at least 10
162 years. The ELN will also need to implement Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) that
163 can be used by commonly used software. Finally, it is important to enable links to internal
164 and external files, as well as file-sharing services and repositories.

165 Another way to facilitate the integration of the ELN into your RDM strategy is to use an open
166 exchange format (see Rule 2 for more details).

167 Rule 8: Build a community

168 To share your experiences, you can build a community within your institution around the
169 ELN you have implemented. This community can focus on user support, which is essential
170 for successful implementation. It can be built around peer-to-peer support and address
171 issues such as accessibility, instructions on how to use the ELN, and problem solving.

172 You can also build or join a community around your ELN outside your institution. Consider
173 maintaining contact with the ELN provider or the open-source community developing the
174 ELN to communicate your needs for further development. Also consider joining a network
175 with other institutions using the same ELN to share experiences, resources (e.g., training
176 videos for open-source ELNs, test questionnaires, needs analysis survey, templates) and
177 solutions (e.g., storage connectivity, integration into your RDM strategy).

178 **Rule 9: Contribute to the ELN**

179 Open-source ELNs allow you both to observe the developments of other users and to make
180 your own contributions. This makes it possible to extend the tool to meet your (discipline-
181 specific) needs and to share these developments in a documented way (e.g., with eLabFTW
182 [16]).

183 An important way to contribute is by improving the core source code. This involves actively
184 participating in the development of the fundamental infrastructure of the ELN, implementing
185 new features, improving existing features and optimising performance.

186 You can also contribute by developing and improving plugins/extensions. These add-ons
187 extend the capabilities of the ELN and help to meet the specific needs of sub-communities.
188 By creating or enhancing these additional components, you can help diversify and enrich the
189 ELN's feature set.

190 Other contributions (e.g. for non-coders) include testing the developer version, reporting
191 bugs with a detailed description of the problem, and writing documentation.

192 **Rule 10: Handle sensitive data appropriately**

193 If you intend to collect sensitive data with the ELN, you should involve your institution's data
194 protection officer in the implementation process to ensure compliance with your institution's
195 data protection regulations and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). These

196 regulations may restrict the physical location and transfer of data, excluding the use of cloud-
197 hosted ELNs [1, 4]. You can also contact your RDM support team to learn more about
198 anonymisation and pseudonymisation services. It is important to note that privacy issues are
199 not addressed by the ELN itself, but rather by how you set it up and store your data.

200 Conclusion

201 ELN implementation should be carried out using a top-down approach: the decision should
202 come from the top, as should the resources for software, support and staff training, the
203 formalisation of ELN use in a policy, and best practices for data and documentation
204 management. To be sustainable, however, ELN use must be driven by personal conviction.
205 Implementing and using an ELN requires time, ongoing support and training, but will be
206 rewarded with increased efficiency, collaboration and trust in your work.

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